

Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center

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Abstract:

Understanding the learning center's acceptance requires analyzing its product, pricing, location, and promotion feasibility. In this premise, this paper analyzed the acceptability of an early childhood learning center. Data needed for this descriptive paper was collected from 195 homeowners using a survey questionnaire that has hurdled the rigorous tests of validity and reliability. The ensuing analysis showed that most homeowners were older women with incomes higher than the average. Moreover, the data gathered indicates a very high level of acceptability for the learning center in terms of product, price, promotion, and place. Meanwhile, no significant difference was observed when respondents were grouped by age, sex, or income. The result implies that age, sex, and income do not significantly impact the level of acceptance of a learning center. Lastly, establishing a learning center is highly possible due to its widespread acceptance and consistent interest across various demographic groups; thus, it will serve as the foundation for a feasibility study.

Keywords: Early Childhood, Learning Center, Acceptability, Feasibility, 4Ps, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Early childhood education has risen to the forefront of public awareness due to various socio-economic changes. While the importance of early education has long been recognized, child care has received more attention in recent years due to fundamental changes in the economy, family relations, and public support. The importance of a home environment in child care has received increased attention, reflecting a landscape portrayed by rising living costs, an increase in dual-income and single-parent households, and greater mobility. These changes underline the importance of accessible and high-quality early childhood education. Amid these changes, the acceptability of an early childhood learning center emerges as a vital aspect, reflecting the changing requirements and expectations of modern families (Essa et al., 2019).

Conversely, in locales such as Talisay, Negros Occidental, a competitive landscape among private preschool organizations exacerbates challenges in accessing education, particularly for families residing in middle-income subdivisions. A learning center within the village is necessary for parents to consider costly alternatives, such as enrolling their children in distant private institutions. Commuting to urban schools entails logistical hurdles, including traffic congestion and exorbitant transportation costs, further burdening working parents. Consequently, the absence of accessible educational hubs within the vicinity strains financial resources and limits educational opportunities. Thus, amid discussions surrounding the establishment of a learning center, the feasibility study seeks to address these disparities by gauging community acceptance and assessing the center's potential to alleviate educational barriers within the village.

Current State of Knowledge

A learning center's appeal can be increased in today's tech-driven educational environment by incorporating technology into teaching strategies and giving students access to pertinent digital resources. Financial aid, flexible payment plans, and scholarships contribute to better inclusivity. Other important factors are the cost of education and the center's accessibility for people from various socioeconomic backgrounds (Mir-Bernal & Sadaba, 2022). The core offerings of the learning center are essential for highlighting high-quality instruction, knowledgeable staff, and an inclusive classroom environment. These offerings include extracurricular activities, academic programs, and distinctive features like specialist courses and technological integration (Mahajan & Golahit, 2020). The value proposition of offering a secure and encouraging learning environment must be reflected in pricing strategies, especially considering parents' financial constraints when raising elementary school-aged children (Chen et al., 2023).

Establishing a welcoming environment in the learning center is crucial to establishing security and comfort, which in turn promotes successful learning outcomes. The staff's warmth, friendliness, and approachability greatly add to this environment, which improves the whole experience for the kids. In addition, the center fosters a friendly atmosphere that encourages parental involvement. Parents who feel respected and at ease tend to participate more in events, activities, and conversations (Karoly, 2016).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored to the Theory of Resource Dependency by Pfeffer and Salancik (2015); it delves into the intricate interplay between the learning center and its external environment. The theory underscores the critical role of external resources, such as funding, partnerships, and community support, in shaping the functioning and success of organizations. By applying resource dependency theory to the study, researchers can better understand the learning center's reliance on external resources and the strategies employed to manage these dependencies effectively.

Analyzing the resource dependencies of the learning center can offer valuable insights into its feasibility and sustainability as an educational initiative within the community. By exploring how the learning center navigates and leverages external resources to support its operations and goals, the study can provide a comprehensive assessment of the acceptability and long-term viability of the educational venture. Understanding the dynamics of resource dependencies within the context of the learning center can inform strategic decision-making and planning processes to enhance the acceptability and success of the educational initiative within the community.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of acceptability of an early childhood learning center. More specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the level of acceptability of a learning center when grouped according to product, price, place, and promotion; 2) the level of acceptability of a learning center when grouped according to age, sex and income; and 3) the significant difference in the level of acceptability of a Learning Center when grouped according to demographics.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, locale of the study, respondents, data gathering instrument, validity and reliability of the instrument, data gathering procedure, analytical schemes, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

A descriptive research design, guided by Sarantakos (2013), was employed to assess the acceptability of a learning center, forming the basis for a feasibility study. This methodology aims to systematically gather and interpret data on consumer preferences, perceived quality, design elements, cost, and satisfaction, utilizing techniques such as surveys or input from retailers and potential customers. By gathering homeowners' opinions, the study aims to determine the viability of establishing a learning center within the village, providing a detailed overview of factors influencing its acceptance.

Respondents

Using Cochran's calculator, this paper used a stratified random sampling technique to determine the respondents (N=195) out of 395 population.

Instruments

This study administered a survey questionnaire to the total homeowners population. It was subjected to validity (4.89 – excellent) and reliability (.964 – excellent). They were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale containing the following scores with range and descriptions: 5- Very High; 4- High; 3- Moderate; 2 – Low, and 1 -Very Low.

Data Gathering Procedures

The study used a survey questionnaire to gather data, and permission to conduct in-person surveys was granted by the village's Homeowners Officers. During house visits, two people who were allocated to Sectors 1 and 2 distributed the questionnaire. Microsoft Excel and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) program were used to numerically code the raw data. The respondent profiles were outlined by statistical analysis using frequency and percentage distributions, and the acceptance level of a learning center was assessed using the arithmetic mean in four areas: product, price, place, and promotion. Moreover, to find significant differences, statistical tests like the Mann-Whitney U test were used.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of acceptability of a learning center when grouped according to product, price, place, and promotion; Objective No. 2 also used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of acceptability of an early childhood learning center when grouped according to age, sex, and income. Objective No. 3 used a comparative-analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of acceptability of an early childhood learning center when grouped according to the variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were given utmost importance in the study. The researcher ensured that respondents were free to participate in the study, that their identities were not revealed, and that the data collected would be kept confidential. Voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and plagiarism were rigorously enforced.

Result and Discussion

This section presents the data obtained in support of the study's objectives. These data have been gathered through answers to questionnaires, counted, tabulated, and analyzed statistically.

Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Product, Price, Place, and Promotion

Table 1
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Product

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....		
1. there is a focus on early childhood development and age-appropriate learning activities.	4.32	Very High Level
2. there is a strong emphasis on individualized learning and personalized attention.	4.33	Very High Level
3. some experienced and qualified teachers specialize in their respective subjects.	4.33	Very High Level
4. there is a diverse range of extracurricular activities offered.	4.30	Very High Level
5. the curriculum is aligned with the national education standards.	4.40	Very High Level
6. it provides a conducive and interactive learning environment.	4.30	Very High Level
7. it provides flexible scheduling options and focuses on client satisfaction.	4.33	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.33	Very High Level

Table 1 shows that the overall mean acceptability of a learning center in the product is 4.33, which is interpreted as very high. The highest mean score is 4.40, interpreted as a very high level on item 5. The lowest mean score is 4.30, interpreted as a very high level on item 4, and item 6. The study's findings show that while homeowners have a positive overall view of the learning center, some areas need improvement, such as offering a range of extracurricular activities and improving the learning environment.

Table 2
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Price

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....		
1. there are competitive and affordable pricing options.	4.32	VeryHigh Level
2. there are discounts or promotions available for siblings or multiple enrollments.	4.27	VeryHigh Level
3. there is overall value for money with high-quality education and resources.	4.29	VeryHigh Level
4. there are available flexible payment plans.	4.28	VeryHigh Level
5. there are customized pricing options for individual needs or specific circumstances.	4.26	VeryHigh Level
6. there are easy and convenient payment methods.	4.33	VeryHigh Level
7. there are transparent pricing policies that are easy to understand and communicate.	4.32	VeryHigh Level
Overall Mean	4.30	Very High Level

Table 2 shows the overall mean on the level of acceptability of a learning center in price, which is 4.30, interpreted as a very high level. The highest mean score is 4.33, interpreted as a very high level on item 6. The lowest mean score is 4.26, interpreted as a very high level on item 5. The result implies that, while homeowners value the convenience of easy payment methods, enhancing the availability of tailored pricing options may enhance the learning center's appeal.

Table 3
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Place

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....		
1. it is conveniently located near my home.	4.55	Very High Level
2. it is accessible and easy to locate	4.58	Very High Level
3. it has a safe and secure environment.	4.59	Very High Level
4. it has a welcoming and child-friendly atmosphere.	4.59	Very High Level
5. it has clean and hygienic facilities.	4.61	Very High Level

6. there is readily and convenient transportation.	4.57	Very High Level
7. additional amenities and nearby facilities enhance the overall learning experience.	4.58	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.58	Very High Level

Table 3 shows that the overall mean level of acceptability of a learning center in place is 4.58, which is interpreted as very high. The highest mean score is 4.61, interpreted as a very high level on item 5. The lowest mean score is 4.55, interpreted as a very high level on item 1. The results of this study imply that, although the perception of the learning center is primarily influenced by aspects such as cleanliness and hygiene, the overall acceptance of the learning center is also greatly influenced by its convenient location.

Table 4
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Promotion

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...		
1. the promotional efforts reflect the school's mission and vision as an educational institution.	4.23	Very High Level
2. the promotional materials effectively communicate the unique features of the learning center.	4.21	Very High Level
3. the promotional materials provide clear and accurate information about the learning programs.	4.22	Very High Level
4. the learning center's promotional activities align with my preferences and communication style.	4.20	High Level
5. the awareness of the learning center's offerings is well-promoted through various channels.	4.18	High Level
6. there are open houses or information sessions where I can visit the facility and learn more about the center's curriculum and approach.	4.23	Very High Level
7. I can easily access information about the center through online platforms or social media channels.	4.21	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.21	Very High Level

Table 4 shows that the overall mean level of acceptability of a learning center in the promotion area is 4.21, which is interpreted a very high. The highest mean score is 4.23, interpreted as a very high level on items 1 and 6. The lowest mean score is 4.18, interpreted as a high level on item 5. This finding implies that while promotional efforts reflecting the school's mission and vision, as well as opportunities for in-person visits, have been positively received by homeowners, there is a need to improve and focus on the promotion of the learning center's offerings through multiple types of channels to create more awareness among the target audience before establishing the learning center.

Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Product, Price, Place, and Promotion when grouped by Age, Sex, and Income

Table 5
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Product according to age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. there is a focus on early childhood development and age-appropriate learning activities.	4.35	Very High Level	4.29	Very High Level
2. there is a strong emphasis on individualized learning and personalized attention.	4.40	Very High Level	4.26	Very High Level
3. some experienced and qualified teachers specialize in their respective subjects.	4.42	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
4. there is a diverse range of extracurricular activities offered.	4.34	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
5. the curriculum is aligned with the national education standards.	4.44	Very High Level	4.36	Very High Level
6. it provides a conducive and interactive learning environment.	4.37	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
7. it provides flexible scheduling options and focuses on client satisfaction.	4.37	Very High Level	4.30	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.38	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level

Table 5 shows the overall mean level of acceptability of a learning center in the product area according to age. The overall mean score of the younger category is 4.38, interpreted as very high, while for the older category, it is 4.28, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score for the younger category is 4.44 in item

5, while for the older category, it is 4.36 in item 5. The lowest mean score for the younger category is 4.34 in item 4, whereas for the older category, it is 4.25 in items 3, 4, and 6. Both age groups perceive a wide range of extracurricular activities, experienced teachers, and an engaging learning environment. However, younger homeowners scored better on average for the various activities offered.

Table 6
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Price according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. there are competitive and affordable pricing options.	4.35	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
2. there are discounts or promotions available for siblings or multiple enrollments.	4.30	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
3. there is overall value for money with high-quality education and resources.	4.33	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
4. there are available flexible payment plans.	4.31	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
5. there are customized pricing options for individual needs or specific circumstances.	4.27	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
6. there are easy and convenient payment methods.	4.31	Very High Level	4.35	Very High Level
7. there are transparent pricing policies that are easy to understand and communicate.	4.32	Very High Level	4.31	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.31	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level

Table 6 shows the overall mean level of acceptability of a learning center in the price area according to age. The overall mean of the younger category is 4.31, interpreted as very high, while for the older category, it is 4.28, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score in the younger category is 4.35 in item 1, while for the older category, it is 4.35 in item 6. The lowest mean score in the younger category is 4.27 in item 5, whereas for the older category, it is 4.36 in items 2, 3, 4, and 5. Despite customized pricing options obtaining the lowest mean score, both age groups favor pricing and payment options regarding educational services.

Table 7
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Place according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....				
1. it is conveniently located near my home.	4.52	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
2. it is accessible and easy to locate	4.56	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
3. it has a safe and secure environment.	4.60	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
4. it has a welcoming and child-friendly atmosphere.	4.59	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
5. it has clean and hygienic facilities.	4.58	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
6. there is readily and convenient transportation.	4.52	Very High Level	4.62	Very High Level
7. additional amenities and nearby facilities enhance the overall learning experience.	4.54	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.56	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level

Table 7 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in place according to age. The overall mean score of the younger categories is 4.56, interpreted as very high, while for the older group, it is 4.61, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score of the younger categories is 4.60 in item 3, while for the older group, it is 4.63 in items 5 and 7. The lowest mean score in the younger category is 4.52 in items 1 and 6, whereas for the older category, it is 4.59 in items 1, 3, and 4. Both younger and older homeowners highly value convenient location and transportation for a learning center, but older homeowners prioritize environment, safety, and ease of access to their house more than younger homeowners.

Table 8
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Promotion according to age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. the promotional efforts reflect the school's mission and vision as an educational institution.	4.20	High Level	4.25	Very High Level
2. the promotional materials effectively communicate the unique features of the learning center.	4.18	High Level	4.23	Very High Level
3. the promotional materials provide clear and accurate	4.28	Very High Level	4.16	High Level

information about the learning programs.

4. the learning center's promotional activities align with my preferences and communication style.	4.24	Very High Level	4.17	High Level
5. the awareness of the learning center's offerings is well-promoted through various channels.	4.20	High Level	4.17	High Level
6. there are open houses or information sessions where I can visit the facility and learn more about the center's curriculum and approach.	4.28	Very High Level	4.18	High Level
7. I can easily access information about the center through online platforms or social media channels.	4.28	Very High Level	4.14	High Level
Overall Mean	4.24	Very High Level	High	4.18 High Level

Table 8 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the promotion area according to age. The overall mean score of the younger categories is 4.24, interpreted as very high, while for the older group, it is 4.18, also interpreted as high. The highest mean score of the younger categories is 4.28 in items 3, 6, and 7, while for the older group, it is 4.25 in item 1. The lowest mean score in the younger category is 4.18 in item 2, whereas for the older category, it is 4.14 in item 7. This reveals how different age groups perceive advertising materials and the accessibility of internet platforms, aiding businesses in aligning their plans with the interests of their target audience.

Table 9
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Product according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....				
1. there is a focus on early childhood development and age-appropriate learning activities.	4.40	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
2. there is a strong emphasis on individualized learning and personalized attention.	4.45	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
3. some experienced and qualified teachers specialize in their respective subjects.	4.45	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
4. there is a diverse range of extracurricular activities offered.	4.37	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
5. the curriculum is aligned with the national education standards.	4.44	Very High Level	4.38	Very High Level
6. it provides a conducive and interactive learning environment.	4.40	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
7. it provides flexible scheduling options and focuses on client satisfaction.	4.37	Very High Level	4.31	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.41	Very High Level	High	4.28 Very High Level

Table 9 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the product area according to sex. The overall mean score of the male categories is 4.41, interpreted as very high, while for females, it is 4.28, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score of the male categories is 4.45 in items 2 and 3, while for females, it is 4.38 in item 5. The lowest mean score in the male category is 4.37 in items 4 and 7, whereas for females, it is 4.25 in items 2, 3, 4, and 6. Males prioritize flexible scheduling and extracurricular activities, reflecting satisfaction, while females value individualized learning, knowledgeable teachers, extracurricular activities, and a supportive learning environment, indicating high regard for these features.

Table 10
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Price according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....				
1. there are competitive and affordable pricing options.	4.38	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
2. there are discounts or promotions available for siblings or multiple enrollments.	4.21	Very High Level	4.31	Very High Level
3. there is overall value for money with high-quality education and resources.	4.37	Very High Level	4.24	Very High Level
4. there are available flexible payment plans.	4.30	Very High Level	4.27	Very High Level
5. there are customized pricing options for individual needs or specific circumstances.	4.33	Very High Level	4.21	Very High Level
6. there are easy and convenient payment methods.	4.42	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
7. there are transparent pricing policies that are easy to understand and communicate.	4.37	Very High Level	4.29	Very High Level

Overall Mean **4.34** **Very High Level** **4.27** **Very High Level**

Table 10 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the price area according to sex. The overall mean score of the male categories is 4.34, interpreted as very high, while for females, it is 4.27, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score of the male categories is 4.42 in item 6, while for females, it is 4.31 in item 2. The lowest mean score in the male category is 4.21 in item 2, whereas for females, it is 4.21 in item 5. This indicates that both males and females rate pricing-related items highly, indicating satisfaction. Males prioritize discounts or promotions, while females value tailored price alternatives.

Table 11
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Place according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. it is conveniently located near my home.	4.58	Very High Level	4.54	Very High Level
2. it is accessible and easy to locate	4.59	Very High Level	4.58	Very High Level
3. it has a safe and secure environment.	4.63	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
4. it has a welcoming and child-friendly atmosphere.	4.62	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
5. it has clean and hygienic facilities.	4.63	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
6. there is readily and convenient transportation.	4.56	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
7. additional amenities and nearby facilities enhance the overall learning experience.	4.59	Very High Level	4.58	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.60	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level

Table 11 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in place according to sex. The overall mean score of the male categories is 4.60, interpreted as very high, while for females, it is 4.57, also interpreted as very high. The highest mean score of the male categories is 4.63 in items 3 and 5, while for females, it is 4.59 in item 5. The lowest mean score in the male category is 4.56 in item 6, whereas for females, it is 4.54 in item 1. This indicates that male homeowners prioritize readily available transportation, while female homeowners value a conveniently located center near their homes.

Table 12
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Terms of Promotion According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. the promotional efforts reflect the school's mission and vision as an educational institution.	4.29	Very High Level	4.19	High Level
2. the promotional materials effectively communicate the unique features of the learning center.	4.25	Very High Level	4.18	High Level
3. the promotional materials provide clear and accurate information about the learning programs.	4.30	Very High Level	4.16	High Level
4. the learning center's promotional activities align with my preferences and communication style.	4.21	Very High Level	4.20	High Level
5. The awareness of the learning center's offerings is well-promoted through various channels.	4.19	High Level	4.18	High Level
6. there are open houses or information sessions where I can visit the facility and learn more about the center's curriculum and approach.	4.29	Very High Level	4.19	High Level
7. I can easily access information about the center through online platforms or social media channels.	4.25	Very High Level	4.18	High Level
Overall Mean	4.25	Very High Level	4.18	High Level

Table 12 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the promotion area according to sex. The overall mean score of the male categories is 4.25, interpreted as a very high level, while for females, it is 4.18, interpreted as a high level. The highest mean score of the male categories is 4.30 in item 3, while for the female group category is 4.20 in item 4. The lowest mean score in the male category is 4.19 in item 5, whereas for females, it is 4.16 in item 3. This indicates that both male and female homeowners value different aspects of promotional activities when evaluating a learning center. Male homeowners prioritize the awareness and promotion of the learning center's offerings through various channels. In contrast, female homeowners prioritize the clarity and accuracy of information provided in promotional materials about the learning programs.

Table 13
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Product According to Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. there is a focus on early childhood development and age-appropriate learning activities.	4.29	Very High Level	4.35	Very High Level
2. there is a strong emphasis on individualized learning and personalized attention.	4.28	Very High Level	4.36	Very High Level
3. some experienced and qualified teachers specialize in their respective subjects.	4.28	Very High Level	4.36	Very High Level
4. there is a diverse range of extracurricular activities offered.	4.32	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
5. the curriculum is aligned with the national education standards.	4.44	Very High Level	4.37	Very High Level
6. it provides a conducive and interactive learning environment.	4.35	Very High Level	4.26	Very High Level
7. it provides flexible scheduling options and focuses on client satisfaction.	4.22	Very High Level	4.42	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.31	Very High Level	4.34	Very High Level

Table 13 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in product according to average family income. The lower monthly income category scored 4.31 overall, interpreted as very high, compared to 4.34 for the higher income category. In item 5, the lower income group scored 4.44, while the higher income group scored 4.42. Conversely, in item 7, the lower income group scored 4.22, and the higher income group scored 4.26. These results reveal slight differences in priorities between income categories, with lower income groups rating flexible scheduling options and client satisfaction slightly lower than higher income groups, who marginally rated a conducive and interactive learning environment lower.

Table 14
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Price According to Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when...				
1. there are competitive and affordable pricing options.	4.33	Very High Level	4.31	Very High Level
2. there are discounts or promotions available for siblings or multiple enrollments.	4.29	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
3. there is overall value for money with high-quality education and resources.	4.34	Very High Level	4.25	Very High Level
4. there are available flexible payment plans.	4.36	Very High Level	4.22	Very High Level
5. there are customized pricing options for individual needs or specific circumstances.	4.32	Very High Level	4.21	Very High Level
6. there are easy and convenient payment methods.	4.40	Very High Level	4.28	Very High Level
7. there are transparent pricing policies that are easy to understand and communicate.	4.32	Very High Level	4.32	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.34	Very High Level	4.26	Very High Level

Table 14 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the price area according to income. For the lower monthly income category, the overall mean score is 4.34, interpreted as very high, compared to 4.26 for the higher income category. The highest mean score for the lower income group is 4.40 in item 6, while for the higher income category, it is 4.32 in item 7. Conversely, the lowest mean score in the lower income group is 4.29 in item 2, while for the higher income category, it is 4.21 in item 5. This suggests that lower income groups prioritize discounts or promotions, while higher income groups value customized pricing options.

Table 15
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Place according to Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....				
1. it is conveniently located near my home.	4.53	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
2. it is accessible and easy to locate	4.59	Very High Level	4.58	Very High Level
3. it has a safe and secure environment.	4.58	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
4. it has a welcoming and child-friendly atmosphere.	4.55	Very High Level	4.62	Very High Level
5. it has clean and hygienic facilities.	4.55	Very High Level	4.65	Very High Level

6. there is readily and convenient transportation.	4.56	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
7. additional amenities and nearby facilities enhance the overall learning experience.	4.55	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.56	Very High Level	4.60	Very High Level

Table 15 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in place according to average family income. The overall mean score of the lower monthly income category is 4.56, interpreted as very high, while the higher monthly income category is 4.60. The highest mean score of the lower monthly income category is 4.59 in item 2, while for the higher monthly income category, it is 4.65 in item 7. The lowest mean score in the lower monthly income category is 4.53 in item 1, while for the higher monthly income category, it is 4.57 in items 1 and 6. Despite slightly lower mean scores, the higher income group shows positive perception and high acceptability of a learning center, indicating potential for improvement in convenient transportation to meet their preferences.

Table 16
Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in terms of Promotion according to Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a potential client, I would likely enroll my child in the learning center when....				
1. the promotional efforts reflect the school's mission and vision as an educational institution.	4.24	Very High Level	4.22	Very High Level
2. the promotional materials effectively communicate the unique features of the learning center.	4.28	Very High Level	4.15	High Level
3. the promotional materials provide clear and accurate information about the learning programs.	4.26	Very High Level	4.18	High Level
4. the learning center's promotional activities align with my preferences and communication style.	4.26	Very High Level	4.15	High Level
5. the awareness of the learning center's offerings is well-promoted through various channels.	4.19	High Level	4.18	High Level
6. there are open houses or information sessions where I can visit the facility and learn more about the center's curriculum and approach.	4.22	Very High Level	4.23	Very High Level
7. I can easily access information about the center through online platforms or social media channels.	4.19	High Level	4.22	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.23	Very High Level	4.19	High Level

Table 16 shows the level of acceptability of a learning center in the promotion area according to average family income. The overall mean score of the lower monthly income category is 4.23, interpreted as a very high level, while the higher monthly income category is 4.19, interpreted as a high level. The highest mean score of the lower monthly income category is 4.28 in item 2, while for the higher monthly income category, it is 4.23 in item 6. The lowest mean score in the lower monthly income category is 4.19 in items 5 and 7, while for the higher monthly income category, it is 4.15 in items 2 and 4. This indicates that the lower monthly income category values well-promoted awareness of the learning center's offerings through various channels and easy access to information on online platforms or social media. Conversely, homeowners in the higher monthly income category prioritize promotional materials that effectively communicate the unique features of the learning center and promotional activities that align with their preferences and communication styles.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Product, Price, Place, and Promotion when grouped by Age, Sex, and Income

Table 17
Difference in the Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Product when grouped according to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	93	103.74	4209.00	0.165	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	92.76				
Sex	Male	73	104.06	4010.50	0.235		Not Significant
	Female	122	94.37				

Monthly Income	Lower	85	98.46	4636.00	0.919	Not Significant
	Higher	110	97.65			

Table 17 shows the difference in the level of acceptability of a learning center according to variables in the product area when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables. The analysis of the data reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean rank scores based on age, as both the younger and older categories have p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the mean rank scores for sex indicate no significant difference, as the p-values for both male and female categories are greater than 0.05, except for the male category having a slightly more significant p-value of 0.235. Additionally, there is no significant difference in mean rank scores based on average family monthly income, as both lower and higher monthly income categories have p-values greater than 0.05. Overall, these results suggest that age, sex, and average family monthly income do not significantly impact the observed mean rank scores.

Table 18
Difference in the Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Price when grouped according to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	93	101.95	4376.00	0.341		Not Significant
	Older	102	94.40				
Sex	Male	73	100.39	4278.50	0.640	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	122	96.57				
Monthly Income	Lower	85	104.58	4116.00	0.144		Not Significant
	Higher	110	92.92				

Table 18 shows the difference in the level of acceptability of a learning center according to variables in price when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables. The analysis of the data indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean rank scores based on age, as both the younger and older categories have p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the mean rank scores for sex show no significant difference, as the p-values for both male and female categories are greater than 0.05, with the male category having a slightly more significant p-value of 0.640. Additionally, there is no significant difference in mean rank scores based on average family monthly income, as both lower and higher monthly income categories have p-values greater than 0.05. These findings suggest that age, sex, and average family monthly income do not have a significant impact on the observed mean rank scores.

Table 19
Difference in the Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Place when grouped according to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	93	99.13	4637.50	0.770		Not Significant
	Older	102	96.97				
Sex	Male	73	100.76	4251.50	0.564	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	122	96.35				
Monthly Income	Lower	85	100.02	4503.50	0.632		Not Significant
	Higher	110	96.44				

Table 19 shows the difference in the level of acceptability of a learning center according to variables in the area place when grouped and compared according to the variables. The analysis of the data reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean rank scores based on age, as both the younger and older categories have p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the mean rank scores for sex indicate no significant difference, as the p-values for both male and female categories are greater than 0.05, with the male category having a slightly higher p-value of 0.564. Additionally, there is no significant difference in mean rank scores based on average family monthly income, as both lower and higher monthly income categories have p-values greater than 0.05. These results suggest that age, sex, and average family monthly income do not have a significant impact on the observed mean rank scores.

Table 20

Difference in the Level of Acceptability of an Early Childhood Learning Center in Promotion when grouped according to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	93	101.95	4375.50	0.342		Not Significant
	Older	102	94.40				
Sex	Male	73	100.58	4265.00	0.616	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	122	96.46				
Monthly Income	Lower	85	101.38	4388.00	0.455		Not Significant
	Higher	110	95.39				

Table 20 shows the difference in the level of acceptability of a learning center according to variables in promotion when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables. The analysis of the data indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean rank scores based on age, as both the younger and older categories have p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the mean rank scores for sex show no significant difference, as the p-values for both male and female categories are greater than 0.05, with the female category having a slightly more significant p-value of 0.616. Additionally, there is no significant difference in mean rank scores based on average family monthly income, as both lower and higher monthly income categories have p-values greater than 0.05. These findings suggest that age, sex, and average family monthly income do not have a significant impact on the observed mean rank scores.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the respondents' profile reflects the potential market for a learning center. The acceptability levels of the learning center were generally high in terms of product, price, and place, while the area of promotion received the lowest mean score. To establish the learning center successfully, it is crucial to prioritize promotional strategies such as awareness campaigns, market-aligned activities, effective materials, and accessible platforms. Overall, the high acceptability across various groupings makes the establishment of the learning center highly feasible. These findings call for actions such as prioritizing promotional strategies, conducting awareness initiatives through various channels, customizing offers based on consumer preferences, creating impactful promotional materials, and leveraging online platforms. These actions will help the learning center thrive from the start and attract prospective customers in a competitive environment.

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